

USE OF ADJECTIVES IN ENGLISH

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Abstract: *The article focuses on information about the use of borrowed words in English, and provides recommendations for reading them in English.*

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As long as English acquisitions are in lexical-semantic relations such as synonymy and antonymy, they are combined with members of certain paradigms into thematic groups. Such thematic groups have their place in the language based on hierarchical (level) relations. Since the vocabulary of the language is developing in accordance with the changes in society, the place of borrowed words plays a primary role in enriching the lexicon. After independence, the direct assimilation of foreign words into our language increased. In particular, learning English is of great importance. Thematic groups of lexemes can be studied based on different classifications. For example, science, art, maritime, railway, agriculture, crafts, construction, trade, medicine, printing, information technology, telegraph, on political, economic, cultural, sports topics and their internal division. lexemes related to military and household topics have their own system. Also, the names of food products, names of drinks, names of clothes, names of household items, names of organizations, names representing the concept of place, names of

fabrics, names of transport vehicles, names of narcotic substances, names of fuel products, names of technical equipment also serve to fill the empty spaces of some thematic groups in the lexicon of the Uzbek language.

These lexemes have their own semantic differences, which differ in what kind of merchandise to sell, total floor area, warehouse space, how many customers can be received at the same time, can provide service, the number of cash registers. , the number of sellers, and the ability to deliver the desired products in quantity also differ. We can see their difference below.

Changes in the semantics of English loanwords from the lexicon of the Uzbek language are significant. takes a leading position in the process of language phenomena such as active participation. Although English borrowings enter our language as names of concepts such as things, events or signs, their etymological history in their own language does not leave anyone indifferent. hooligan in the sense of hooligan [visual. hooligan] lexeme from the Irish noun Houlihan; a very small person; Lilliput in the meaning of dwarf [visual. Lilliputian] in the name of the fantastic dwarf people of the fictional country of Lilliputia in the famous writer J. Swift's "Gulliver's Travels"; whatman [visual Whatman] on behalf of J. Whatman, the owner of the paper factory; gaymoritis used in the field of medicine [visual. Highmore] on behalf of the English physician and anatomist N. Gaymore; Lewisite lewisite] on behalf of the American chemist W. Lewis (Lewis); mackintosh [visual Mackintosh] after Mackintosh, a Scottish chemist who invented damp-proof cloth; rugby used in sports [visual rugby] from the English town of Rugby; badminton [visual Badminton] on behalf of the town of Badminton in England; reglan [visual Raglan] from the English general Raglan; sheviot [visual cheviot] from the name of the Cheviot hills (Cheviot hills), where the breed of soft-

wooled sheep in Scotland is bred; Boycott expressing a political concept [visual. The lexeme Boycott] is taken from the name of a large English landowner Ch.K. In general, the names of food products, names of drinks, names of clothes, names of household goods, names of organizations, names meaning the concept of place, names of cloth, names of means of transportation, drugs names, names of fuel products, names of technical equipment also serve to fill the empty places of some thematic groups in the lexicon of the Uzbek language.

2. Types and lexicographical interpretation of possessive words according to their structure

In the process of word acquisition before independence, it can be observed that some lexemes were adapted to the phonetic, lexical, morphological or syntactic phenomena of the Russian language and were absorbed into the lexicon of the Uzbek language. The lexeme of training is also a product of this phenomenon and represents the concept of regular exercises and training in order to acquire certain qualities or maintain them. The original version of this lexeme is training after independence [visual. training - to teach, to bring up, to practice] was adopted.

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